

DEVELOPMENT OF UNPREPARED SPEECH OF STUDENTS IN THE WORKS OF V. RASPUTIN "LESSONS OF FRENCH" AND A. S. MAKARENKO "PEDAGOGICAL POEM".

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Abstract: One of the most important tasks on the stage of inclusive education is to develop students' - future teachers' skills of unprepared spontaneous speech. Works of fiction can be an effective stimulus for active thinking and speech activity of students. This article is devoted to the development of unprepared speech of students - philology students on the material of the works of V. Rasputin - "The Lesson of the Frenchman". Rasputin - "The lessons of the French", A. S. Makarenko's "Pedagogical poem".

Key words: speech, skill, unprepared speech, philologist, child's personality, ode, educator.

A teacher should know his subject really well, and then he will be respected and listened to, even if he is a harsh person. But no matter how nice you are, no matter how much candy you feed them, if you don't know your subject, they won't appreciate you for a minute. You'll always be the object of ridicule and mockery. All sorts of tricks and trickery will be prepared for you, all because of your lack of respect. (Makarenko).

The appeal to non-adapted literary texts with their non-standard construction, the presence of subtext, figurative language, rich emotional content allows for the transition from situational and contextual speech to the production of an unprepared statement.

One of the most important tasks at the stage of inclusive education is the development of unprepared spontaneous speech skills among the students - future teachers. Works of fiction can be an effective stimulus for students' active thinking and speech activity.

A prerequisite for the success of such work is a purposeful, well thought-out selection of works of fiction to be read. Assuming the ultimate goal of "going out" into spontaneous speech, the choice of text should take into account not only the poignancy of the plot, but also the relevance of the topics and themes of the work to the students' interests, in particular their professional sphere of activity. For example, for future teachers will be naturally interested in works devoted to pedagogical work, reflecting the complexity and versatility of the teaching profession.

Skilfully organized discussion of such works encourages students to express their own opinions of world outlook, polemical or evaluative nature and arouses their desire for professional communication.

Let us turn to the works of famous writers V. Rasputin - "Lessons of French", A. S. Makarenko "Pedagogical Poem". Despite the fact that these works were written in the 30-70's, their pedagogical problems have not lost their relevance: situations to some extent similar to the described, can meet in the practice of modern teachers.

The content and linguistic complexity of these works requires a sufficiently high command of the language, so we start working with the texts of the writers in the second half of the course and in inclusive teaching.

At this stage, work on the development of speech skills and abilities should have the following orientation: from prepared speech on the basis of one topic to unprepared speech on an inter-thematic basis[1]. The prepared statement is built on the basis of the factual content of the work: it is a description of an event or action of the hero, the transfer of internal state of the character, the story about the development of the image during the narrative. Gradually the boundaries of the topic should be broadened, supplementing it with references to the students' personal experience and understanding of what is happening. In line with this, a task is formulated, for example, to tell about some action of a character and express their attitude towards it, to express their agreement or disagreement with some judgments of the characters, to express their point of view on the problem in question. Such tasks require students to make an independent prepared statement on a certain topic.

For example, when discussing the story "French Lessons" by V. Rasputin, special attention should be paid to the characters of the teacher Lydia Mikhailovna and the school principal Vasily Andreevich. The students immediately note that these people's views on the upbringing of children differ significantly. Students should be asked to evaluate the actions and deeds of both teachers. Here it is also useful to refer to the students' own recent school history and ask them to comment on which teachers their children value more.

A novel-poem by A.S. Makarenko, educator and writer, reveals the history of the birth and development of the Gorky colony. The first pupils were juvenile delinquents: adolescents, young boys and girls. Its first inmates were juvenile delinquents: adolescents, young men and later homeless children. The moral revolution in their upbringing did not happen immediately, but in the long, difficult and self-sacrificing struggle of the teachers and educators headed by Makarenko for a highly cultured personality, morally bright, with a developed sense of duty and honour.

In the Gorky work collective of educators, adults and children were united above all by learning, industrial-labour relations, a common working concern for a better tomorrow, a certain style ("spirit") of the colony: a major tone, a combination of respect and exactingness, a sense of dignity, a sense of country and much more.

Makarenko proved that the educational collective, the collective organization of the life and activities of the colonists is the most effective method of educating the personality, the individuality of each pupil.

Not always and not all the deeds of the heroes are unquestionable. The students' attention should be drawn to the complexity of the situation. Who is right: a teacher or an educator who respects the law, who sees a teenager as a human being and a personality who must not be humiliated, but who violates the letter of the law with his/her actions? The question is not easy. This is why there is usually a discussion in the class.

The following questions and tasks can be used to discuss the work "The Pedagogical Poem".

1. How did the teacher, Ekaterina Grigorievna, find an approach to the pupils in the colony?
2. How did the pupils treat Lydia Petrovna?
3. What was the first pupils' attitude towards the teachers and educators in the colony?
4. Describe how Makarenko struck a pupil and why?
5. Name the first pupils of the colony.
6. Why did not all the pupils succeed in being re-educated?

Such organization of work on the development of unprepared speech gives, as experience shows, the necessary results: from discussing events depicted in a work of fiction, students "imperceptibly" and logically shift to collective reflection and discussion of general professional issues, i.e. conditions for natural communication are created in which the emerging need for spontaneous unprepared speech is realized.

After the reading and discussion of these literary works, a final lesson is held at the end of the series. This will be based on a discussion of various issues related to pedagogical work.

In order to get the students actively involved from the very beginning of the lesson, the homework could be to prepare a detailed answer to the question that summarises the pedagogical issues of all the works discussed. What kind of influence do you think children have on their educators? Have you observed examples of such influence? How do you rate them? What theme is common to all the works you have read?

Formulate the problems posed by Rasputin and Makarenko in their works? Which of the two works made the greatest impression on you and why? Compare the attitudes of teachers and educators towards their pupils and wards? Was there a teacher you would like to imitate in your life? Why?

A discussion started by such questions will then develop according to its own laws. The teacher in such a situation should not dominate the classroom but become an equal interlocutor, skillfully encouraging and guiding the discussion. If the lesson is organized well, this specific guiding role will not be noticed by the students and will not inhibit their speech activity.

To conclude the article, these works have touched on many aspects of the human side, such as: the personality of the child (teenager); love of work; respect for oneself and others; building a strong team. They are books about the work of teachers and their students. It is an ode to humanity and morality, and these values are imperishable in any era: "A man should have only one speciality - he should be a big man, a real man".

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